

Goods and Services Tax: The Game Changer

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ABSTRACT

GST has been a landmark in the Indian tax system situation, increasing productivity and addressing tax evasion and corruption issues. India follows a dual tax arrangement where both state and national governments levy taxes. Even though GST has been hailed as a game-changer in India and is a recent phenomenon, it is essential to study whether it is a panacea for all our tax issues. In conclusion, this review has explained that the implementation of GST has been a game-changer for India in boosting the economy, GDP, improving productivity in the domestic market, drawing FDI, reducing the overall tax burden to the consumer and manufacturer alike, etc. Its initial implementation has been confusing as far as registration and paperwork was concerned.

KEYWORDS: GST, GDP, Direct Tax, Indirect Tax.

1. INTRODUCTION

GST (Goods & Services Tax) is a single indirect tax on manufacture, supply, and consumption of goods and services which has replaced other taxes such as excise duty, VAT, services tax, service tax, sales tax, etc. It is of four types: CGST (Central GST), SGST (State GST) and IGST (Intra-state GST), UTGST (Union Territory GST). It differs from income tax as it is the consumption tax, and income tax is the tax on profit or income. In India, a GST registered dealer must obtain a 15 digit number (GSTIN) essential while filling one's GST returns. Businesses below an aggregate of fewer than twenty lakhs are exempt from paying the GST returns in most parts of India, except for Uttarakhand, which is ten lakhs and less (Mitra, 2017). In 1954, France was the first country in the world to adopt GST as an indirect tax arrangement, and to date, 164 countries have adopted this tax system to improve their revenue in an unbiased and transparent manner (Garg, 2014 and Kankipati, 2017). Most of these countries, except for Canada and Brazil, have a single tax structure. Like Canada and Brazil, India follows a dual tax arrangement where tax is levied by both state and national governments (Kankipati, 2017).

GST has been a landmark in the Indian tax system, which increases productivity and addresses issues such as evasion of tax and corruption. Moreover, it makes products more affordable at reasonable prices, giving us good standing in domestic and international markets. The GST has a 4-tier configuration for goods that range from 0-18% with two standard rates of 12&18%. This configuration has helped reduce the cost of logistics and has reduced the overall tax burden to the consumer as more than 50 percent of the necessary items are 0 rated. Five per cent is charged on essential items, and 28 percent is on very few goods (Mitra, 2017). But on the downside of GST is that it may not be favourable for all industries, such as insurance companies, as the rising policy cost can impact insurance dissemination in India. There are some problems with the compliance burden on businesses as it has double charging components, i.e. the tax is charged both by the central and the state government (Khaitan, 2014). Even though GST has been hailed as a game-changer in India and

is a recent phenomenon, it is essential to study whether it is a panacea for all our tax issues. Therefore this review is going to explore some of the problems related to GST.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 GST and Real estate

In India, for the buyers, the under-construction flats GST is 5% compared to 12% pre-GST and no GST with properties with a completion certificate, which has helped the consumers. But this has negatively affected the developers as the buyers are not interested in under-construction properties and have a "wait and watch" approach. In Malaysia, the construction cost of a house has increased by five percent after introducing GST in April 2015 (Hisyam, 2015). Even in Sweden (Englund *et al.*, 1995), the construction material cost has increased by twelve percent, and the overall increase is 9.5%, and in Australia by 10% (ACCC, 2000). In the real estate sector, it has been told that the housing property is exempt from GST. Still, the fine print is that the cost of construction materials, developing and selling is not. The cost of total production has become higher, causing a burden on the developers who will eventually pass it on to the buyers to maintain their profits (Nurul, 2014 and Zainal *et al.*, 2016).

2.2 GST and its impact on inflation

GST had seen a sharp rise in inflation In Canada, Malaysia, Australia, New Zealand immediately after its implementation, attributed to consumers' increased purchasing activity before the new tax was implemented. This has caused the economy to contract for a while post-GST before returning to normalcy after some time (Gelardi, 2014 and Palil and Ibrahim, 2011).

2.3 GST and the Retail Sector

Retail in India contributes 10% of the GDP. In India, the retail sector is divided into organised (<20%) and the rest is the unorganised retail zone. Pre-GST there were about eighty-three lakh registered taxpayers for VAT, excise, etc. but post GST; this is poised to increase by two lakhs. The transition to GST has impacted business with the stored existing stock, especially by the unorganised retail sector as it mainly deals in a cash payment. The positive side is that the unorganised retail industry will have to participate in the taxpaying regimen henceforth. The government has dissuaded purchasing from unregistered dealers as there will reverse tax on registered dealers themselves (Tripathi, 2018). The benefits of GST on the retail are reduced taxes, improved supply chain efficacy; better input tax credit; better business across the states; freedom to implement new business strategies, and beneficial for start-ups as they have to register their business set-up once and reap benefits of taxation with the new GST laws (Tripathi, 2018).

2.4 GST and the Indian economy

GST has boosted the manufacturing sector post GST with 18% as slated rates for industrial products. In India, medicines that treat diabetes, HIV, and malaria are at 5% and the rest at 12%. GST has benefited the generic drug market as well as medical tourism due to an abridged tax structure. MSME has helped due to lower taxes of 18-22% as compared to 32% pre-GST. There is an increase in the GST from 15-18% in the Banking zone, making it marginally costly to the consumer. Post-GST, under the term service, interest earned by the bank, inter-sale or purchase of foreign currency, and services of reserve bank are all taxed under GST. The functioning of the banking sector is now burdened with extra work while registering branches, filing returns, tax invoicing, etc. in short, they have to deal with massive up-gradations and complexities in the system (Kamruddin and Misab, 2018 and Special Seminar, 2018). The E-commerce industry is also not very happy as they have to pay 1% as TCS (Tax Collected at Source) post- GST.

2.5 GST and its ramifications

Implementation of GST has a few teething problems; for example, it needs training and computer availability by small business owners; fifty-one per cent had issues with paperwork; 28% with registration; twelve percent were utterly unaware, nine percent had problems with customer bargaining, and 4% with consumer satisfaction (Ahmed, 2016 and Seminar Special, 2018).

2.6 Some highlights of GST impact

- According to the Central Statistical Organization, India, the economy has grown by 8.2% in the June 2018 quarter, and in the future, it may remain steady at 7-7.5%.
- The GST collections between November 2017- April 2018 were 94,016 crores.

- The consumer is benefitted by reduced tax burden on goods by 25-30%
- 50% increase in the number of indirect taxpayers, i.e. 3.4 million
- Tax on retail gains to 20% from 12%
- Imported items will be costlier at 20% from 16%
- Hotel rooms have a tariff of 18% on rooms ranging from 2500/- to 7500/- and 28% on more than 7500/-
- 18% GST on pesticides has increased the farmer's issues
- Dining is expensive at 20% on the overall bill as compared to the earlier 18.5%
- Phone bills and buying imported handsets has escalated
- Steel is taxed at 18% (Seminar Special, 2018)

3. CONCLUSION

This review has explained that GST implementation has been a game-changer for India to boost the economy, GDP, improve productivity in the domestic market, draw FDI, reduce the overall tax burden to the consumer and manufacturer alike, etc. It has some hitches like stressing out the consumer in case of buying adequate health insurance policies. Its initial implementation has been confusing as far as registration and paperwork were concerned.

4. REFERENCES

1. Ahmad, M.A.R. (2016), "Introducing GST in Malaysia. Two day National Seminar on GST and Digital Economy- Implications on Trade and Commerce", *International Journal of Research in Management and Social Sciences*, Vol. 6(1), IX-Part 1.
2. Australian Competition and Consumer Commission. (ACCC), [au]. (2000).
3. Englund, P.; Hendershott, P.H. and Turner, B. (1995), "The tax reform and the housing market", *Swedish Economic Policy Review*, Vol. 2, pp. 3195-356.
4. Garg, G. (2014), "Basic Concepts and Features of Goods and Services Tax in India", *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management*, Vol. 2(2), pp. 542-549.
5. Gelardi, A.M. (2014), "Value Added Tax and Inflation: A Graphical and Statistical Analysis", *Asian Journal of Finance and Accounting*, Vol. 6(1).
6. Hisyam, K. (2015), GST Impact on p\ Property less than 5%., Says WTW.
7. Kamruddin, S. and Misab, P.T. (2018), "Impact of GST on Banking Sector: An Overview. Seminar Special (January- March 2018), Two day National Seminar on GST and Digital Economy- Implications on Trade and Commerce", *International Journal of Research in Management and Social Sciences*, Vol. 6(1), IX-Part 1.
8. Kankipati, A. K. (2017), "A Journey of Goods and Services Tax (GST) and Structural Impact of GST on the Growth of GDP in India", *International Journal of Journalism and Communication*, Vol. 2(2), pp. 19-22.
9. Khaitan, S. (2014), Goods, and Service Tax: A Game Changer. Insights, 3(10). www.ruchelaw.com.
10. Mitra, P.B. (2017), "GST- A Game Changer", *International Journal of Management Research and Social Science*, Vol. 4(1).
11. Nurul, I. D. (2014), GST Poser on Properties. Personal Money: PwC Malaysia Report. Pp. 20-22.
12. Palil, M.R. and Ibrahim, M.A. (2011), "The Impact of Goods and Services Tax (GST) on Middle-Income Earners in Malaysia", *World Review of Business Research*, Vol. 1 (3).
13. Seminar Special (January- March 2018), "Two day National Seminar on GST and Digital Economy- Implications on Trade and Commerce", *International Journal of Research in Management and Social Sciences*, Vol. 6(1), IX-Part 1.
14. Tanvi and Narwal, Karampal (2017), "Comparative Analysis of Corporate Effective Tax Burden between Manufacturing and Service Sector in Developing Countries: An Empirical Study in India", *MERC Global's International Journal of Management*, Vol. 5, Issue 1, pp. 19-28.
15. Tripathi, S.K. (2018), Goods and Services Tax (GST): Benefit for Small retailers. Swaranjali Publications.
16. Zainal, R.; Teng, T.C., Mohamed, S. (2016), "Construction cost and Housing Prices: Impact of Goods and Service Tax", *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, Vol. 6(S7), pp. 16-20.

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